

The Japanese workers⁶ reported the triazole (IV, R=4-pyridyl) to have m.p. 284-85°, but this triazole now described, characterised as picrate, m.p. 223-25° (decomp.) and nitrate m.p. 143° (decomp.) and by element analysis of the picrate, nitrate and triazole itself has been found to have m.p. 210°.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-(4-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol (III, R = 4-pyridyl): An intimate mixture of isonicotinic acid hydrazide (I, R=4-pyridyl) (20 g.) and thiourea (11.4 g.) was heated in a r.b. flask in an oil bath at 125-30° for six hours. The mixture gradually melted and the reaction between the two components of the mixture was realised by the formation of ammonia. Heating was discontinued (after about six hours) when the evolution of ammonia practically had ceased and the reaction mixture was cooled followed by dilution with water (50 ml.) and stirring. To this dilute caustic soda (10 ml.) was added and thereby practically the entire mass dissolved. After charcoal treatment the yellow coloured solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid to neutral pH. The white crystalline material that separated was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, to afford III (R=4-pyridyl), yield 12 g., m.p. 320-22° (decomp.) ($\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 246 m μ , 317 m μ) (log ϵ = 4.35, 3.52 respectively). Found, C, 47.7%, H, 3.4%; and N, 31.25%. Calc. for C₇H₆N₄S: C, 47.2%, H, 3.4% and N, 31.4%.

3-(p-nitrophenyl)-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol (III, R=p-nitrophenyl) was prepared exactly as above from p-nitro benzoyl hydrazine in about 47% yield. The triazole is light yellow needle shaped crystalline material, m.p. 240° (decomp.).

Found N, 25.3%, calc for C₈H₆N₄O₂S: N, 25.2%.

1-Benzoyl-thiosemicarbazide (II, R=C₆H₅) was prepared in 46.5% yield, exactly as the previous experiment and was purified by crystallisation from water in white needles, m.p. 198° (decomp.) (Lit⁵, m.p. 198°) (decomp.).

Found N, 21.4%, calc. for C₈H₉N₃OS: N, 21.5%.

1-Nicotinyl thiosemicarbazide was also prepared in 45.4%. Yield exactly as above and was purified by crystallisation from water in white needles, m.p. 298-300° (decomp.)

Found N, 28.43% calc. for C₇H₈N₄OS: N, 28.6%.

3-Phenyl-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol (III, R=C₆H₅): 1-Benzoyl thiosemicarbazide (II, R=C₆H₅) (9.75 g.) was added to alcoholic solution (60 ml.) of sodium ethoxide prepared from metallic sodium (1.15 g.) and the mixture was heated to reflux for six hours protected from moisture on water bath. The reaction mixture after being cooled was concentrated on water bath to about 15 ml. under reduced pressure followed by dilution with water to 30 ml. under external cooling. The resulting solution was brought to neutral pH with hydrochloric acid and the crystalline solid that separated was purified by crystallisation from ethanol to afford (III, R=C₆H₅) in white needles, 3.4 g., m.p. 255-56, (Lit⁶, m.p. 256°).

Found: N, 23.5%, Calc for C₈H₇N₃S: N, 23.7%.

3-(3-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole-5-thiol (III, R=3-pyridyl) was prepared exactly as (III,

6. Shigeru Joshida and Mboji Asai, *J. Pharm. Chem. Japan*, 1954, **74**, 946; *Chem. Abst.*, 1955, **49**, 10937.

R=C₆H₅) from (II, R=3-pyridyl) in white shining needles, in 40.2% yield, m.p. 282° (decomp.).

Found: N, 31.3%, calc. for C₇H₆N₄S: N, 31.5%.

3-(4-pyridyl)-1,2,4-triazole (IV, R=4-pyridyl): To a stirred solution of concentrated nitric acid (20 ml.), water (40 ml.) and sodium nitrite (0.02 g.) was added 5-(4-pyridyl) 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (6.4 g.) in small instalments. The temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 45° in a water bath. After the addition was over, it was stirred for one hour more and was cooled to 0°. The nitric acid salt that separated was purified by crystallisation from minimum amount of water in white needles to afford nitric acid salt of (IV, R=4-pyridyl), 3.1 g, m.p. 143° (decomp.).

Found: N, 33.3%, calc. for C₇H₆N₄, HNO₃: N, 33.48%.

From the aqueous solution of the above nitric acid salt the triazole (IV, R=4-pyridyl) separated at neutral pH and was purified by crystallisation from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 210°, yield 2.3 g. [$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 246 m μ (log ϵ =4.02)]

Found: C, 56.5%, H, 4.2% and N, 38.3%. calc. for C₇H₆N₄: C, 56.7%, H, 4.04% and N, 38.4%.

The *picrate* of the above triazole was prepared from its alcoholic solution in yellow needles, m.p. 223-25° (decomp.).

Found: N, 25.64%, calc. for C₇H₆N₄, C₆H₃N₃O₇: N, 26.1%.

The other triazoles were prepared exactly as above from the corresponding triazole -5-thiols. The characteristics of these triazoles are given in the table I.

TABLE I

Triazole	m.p.	Yield	Analyses	
			Found	Calculated
3-phenyl-1,2,4-triazole*	123°	56.7%	N, 28.7%	C ₈ H ₇ N ₃ requires N, 28.9%
3- <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl-1,2,4-triazole	252°-56° (decomp.)	47.0%	N, 29.2%	C ₈ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ requires N, 29.48%
3-(3-pyridyl) 1,2,4-triazole**	Nitric acid salt, m.p. 170-72° (decomp.) Picrate 210-212°	48.2% on the basis of nitric acid salt	For nitric acid salt N, 32.9% For picrate N, 25.7%	C ₇ H ₆ N ₄ , HNO ₃ requires N, 33.48% C ₇ H ₆ N ₄ , C ₆ H ₃ N ₃ O ₇ requires N, 26.1%

*Lit[†] m.p. 121°

**The triazole is hygroscopic and as such was isolated as nitric acid salt.